

The role of solvation models on the computed absorption and emission spectra: the case of fireflies oxyluciferin

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Abstract:

Considering the effect of the surrounding is often crucial to successfully simulate the absorption and emission spectra. In this work we tested different solvation models to compute the transition energies and simulate the spectra of oxyluciferin, the molecule responsible for the light emission in fireflies, which chemical form is still under debate. We show that, within the PCM model, the SS formalism is suitable for computing the transition energies of the oxyluciferin derivatives characterized by a large charge transfer character. Whereas, the LR approach could be used for the derivatives where an almost negligible charge transfer takes place. Moreover, we demonstrate that explicit solvation models, applied by QM/MM calculations, are needed to reproduce the experimental transition energies. In addition, the effect of considering a statistical number of conformations on the spectral shape has been analyzed, concluding that only in this way the experimental shape is achieved. Finally, the effect of the solvation model (implicit or microsolvation) used to simulate the vibrationally resolved spectra has been analyzed. Some differences arise when considering the implicit solvation compared to the gas phase vibrational spectra whereas, small changes were found when including explicit water molecules within a microsolvated model.

I. Introduction

The calculation of vertical electronic transition energies is crucial in order to simulate the absorption and emission spectra. These spectra can be compared with the experimental ones or can be used to predict the spectral properties of novel compounds. However, the simulation of absorption and emission spectra is not an easy task as in most cases, the effect of the environment (*e.g.* solvent or protein surroundings) plays a key role. The complexity of these studies arises from the coupling between the relaxation processes of both the chromophore and the surrounding.

In this regard, two solvation models are the most widely used: explicit and implicit models. In explicit models, the atomistic representation of the solvent molecules is kept and hence, the direct solute-solvent interactions are considered. However, many solvent configurations are required to achieve vertical electronic transition energies statistical averaging.

When working with implicit models, the solvent is described as a polarizable dielectric characterized by the macroscopic dielectric constant (ϵ), being one of the most popular models the polarizable continuum model (PCM).¹ Here, the explicit interactions between the solute and solvent molecules are not considered. A complication that arises from implicit models is the response of the solvent to the changes of the solute charge density, leading to the non-equilibrium and equilibrium regimes.² In non-equilibrium calculations, only the solvent electron density (fast component) is polarized by the change of the solute charge density change in the final state whereas, in equilibrium calculations both, the solvent electron density and its nuclear motions (slow component) are polarized. In general,

the non-equilibrium regime is used when computing fast processes such as absorption and emission processes, whereas the equilibrium one is used for slower processes such as geometry optimizations.

Moreover, the difference between the linear response (LR)^{3,4} and the state specific (SS)⁵⁻⁷ formalisms is another complexity of implicit models. In the SS formalism, the fast component of the solvent response is calculated using the difference of the electronic density between the final and the initial state. For LR formalism, the response of the fast component of the solvent is calculated using the transition density.

A new approach was developed by *Caricato et al*⁸ called state-specific corrected linear response (cLR), which corrects the LR excitation energies by introducing state specific solvent responses.

Apart from the calculation of the absorption or emission energies, the simulation of the spectral shape is crucial to compare them with the experimental data. In this regard, the consideration of vibrational normal modes is sometimes essential to reproduce the shape.⁹⁻¹⁴ The Franck-Condon (FC)^{15,16} approximation is one of the most widely used to simulate the vibrationally resolved spectra, which considers the transition dipole moment as a constant, independent of the nuclear coordinates around the equilibrium geometry.

However, in the cases where there are weak or forbidden transitions, including a linear variation of the dipole moment with respect to the nuclear coordinates is necessary, giving rise to the Herzberg-Teller (HT) approximation.^{17,18} The consideration of both the FC and HT approximation is known as the FCHT method.¹⁹

Figure 1. Chemical forms of natural oxyluciferin (black) and the corresponding synthetic analogues (blue) under study.

The aim of this study is mainly to show the key role of solvation on the simulated absorption and emission spectra. As the study case, we have selected the molecule responsible of light emission in fireflies, so-called oxyluciferin, and its analogues (Figure 1).^{20–22} Firefly oxyluciferin can coexist in six different chemical forms due to inter-exchange reactions (*e.g.* keto/enol tautomerization or protonation/deprotonation).^{23–26} For this reason, still its chemical form is under debate and so, the simulation of the absorption and emission spectra is crucial to get insight into its chemical form *in vivo*.

In this work, the solvent effect on the absorption and emission spectra of oxyluciferin has been evaluated by using both explicit (considering a statistical number of conformations using an explicit model of the solvent) and implicit (LR, cLR and SS formalisms) solvent models. The results obtained are compared with the experimental data.²⁵ Apart from the absorption and emission maxima, the general shape of the spectra has been analyzed. In this regard, the vibrationally resolved spectra have been computed using different solvation models.

II. Methods

QM Calculations

All calculations have been performed at the DFT and TD-DFT level of theory for the ground and excited states, respectively. The B3LYP^{27,28} functional and the 6-311g(2d,p) basis set were used for all calculations after performing a benchmark with different basis sets and DFT functionals (Table S1, S2 and S3).

The absorption ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ at the ground state optimized geometry) and emission ($S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ at the first excited state optimized geometry) energies were calculated in the gas phase and with different solvation models both, implicit and explicit. In all cases water has been selected as the solvent. For implicit solvation, the polarizable continuum model (PCM)¹ was used, the geometries have been optimized using the equilibrium regime and the vertical transitions computed within the non-equilibrium regime. For the transition energies, the LR, cLR and SS (as implemented in Gaussian 09²⁹) approaches have been applied. All calculations have been performed with Gaussian 09²⁹ package.

In order to check the charge transfer (CT) character of the vertical transitions, the CT distance (d_{CT} in Å) and H index, measuring the spread of the positive and negative regions of the CT (in Å), have been calculated according to the methodology proposed for push-pulled molecules by Le Bahers and coworkers (Table S4).^{30,31} Moreover, to visualize the electronic density redistribution and the possible intramolecular CT we calculate the difference between the total densities of the excited and ground states (EDD) as provided by TD-DFT. The isosurfaces have been plotted with the Chemcraft code, considering a contour threshold of 0.004 a.u (Figure S1).³²

MD simulation

MD simulations of 10 ns have been performed with Amber14³³ in order to obtain a statistical number of snapshots to simulate the absorption and emission spectra (see Supporting Information for further details). The TIP3P parameters were used for the water molecules. Regarding the parameters of oxyluciferin derivatives, we have started with the ones obtained from the QM calculation in the gas phase. Then, consecutive reparametrization steps have been performed until reaching spectral shape convergence as explained in the Supporting Information and elsewhere.³⁴

QM/MM Calculations

Snapshots from the MD were taken as starting structures for QM/MM transition energy calculation. The oxyluciferin derivative is described at the QM level while the water molecules are treated at the MM level. The QM/MM calculations have been carried out using a QM/MM coupling scheme³⁵ between Gaussian09 and Tinker.³⁶ In particular, the interaction between the Mulliken charges of the QM part and the external electrostatic potential of the MM part was computed by the electrostatic potential fitted (ESPF) method.³⁵ The microiterations technique³⁷ was used to converge the MM subsystem geometry for every QM minimization step. For the absorption spectra simulation, three excited states were considered. A gaussian convolution of the absorption and emission energies of 100 snapshots was performed, using a full-width at half-maximum of 0.2 eV.

Vibronic spectra

Vibrationally resolved spectra have been computed on the basis of the TD-DFT vibrational signatures by using both, the Franck–Condon (FC) and the Franck–Condon–Herzberg–Teller (FCHT) approximations as implemented in Gaussian 09.^{15,16,19,38} The FCHT spectra resemble the FC ones (Figure S4), so only the FCHT spectra are shown in the main text. The band broadening was simulated by Gaussian functions with half-widths at half-maximum (HWHM) of 135 cm⁻¹. The vibrationally resolved absorption and emission spectra have been simulated in gas phase but also considering different solvation models. In particular, we have considered the solvent with the PCM method but also by microsolvation (both in gas phase and with PCM). For the microsolvation, we have taken 5 snapshots of the MD simulation and kept the water molecules within a radius of 3 Å around the heteroatoms of oxyluciferin. Then, the structure has been optimized in the ground and in the excited state, followed by frequency calculations. It should be noted that to compute the vibrational resolved spectra, the structures of the minima in the ground and in the excited state should be similar. For this reason, we had to keep frozen the water molecules orientation of the ground state minimum during the optimization in the excited state.

III. Results and Discussion

In this section it is going to be presented and discussed the effect of the explicit and implicit solvation models (LR, cLR and SS formalisms) on the absorption and emission spectra. In particular, the section is divided into the effect on: *i)* the vertical transitions energies and *ii)* the spectral shape, considering both the vibronic and the statistical effect.

i) Vertical transition energies.

The energy of the S₀→S₁ (absorption) and S₁→S₀ (emission) vertical transitions have been computed for all the oxyluciferin natural forms and their synthetic analogues in gas phase and using both, explicit and implicit (LR, cLR and SS formalisms) solvation models (Table 1). Before analyzing the data it should

Table 1. Absorption and emission energies of oxyluciferin natural forms (black) and their analogues (blue) computed in gas phase (GP), using implicit (LR, cLR and SS) and explicit (QM/MM) solvation models with the B3LYP functional and the 6-311G(2d,p) basis set. Experimental values are also given.

	E_{GP}^{abs}	E_{LR}^{abs}	E_{cLR}^{abs}	E_{SS}^{abs}	E_{QMMM}^{abs}	E_{exp}^{abs}	E_{GP}^{emi}	E_{LR}^{emi}	E_{cLR}^{emi}	E_{SS}^{emi}	E_{QMMM}^{emi}	E_{exp}^{emi}
Phenol-keto	3.36	3.12	3.07	2.83	3.24	3.19	-	2.80	2.61	2.26	2.33	2.36
Phenol-cycle	3.33	3.11	3.08	2.84	3.18	3.19	-	2.79	2.67	2.32	2.36	2.36
Phenolate-keto	2.60	2.50	2.60	2.63	2.56	2.57	2.27	2.32	2.33	2.33	2.05	1.96
Phenolate-cycle	2.57	2.47	2.57	2.61	2.56	2.57	2.26	2.31	2.31	2.30	2.01	1.95
Phenol-enol	3.43	3.28	3.34	3.25	3.41	3.38	2.96	2.76	2.82	2.73	2.76	2.79
OMe-enol	3.39	3.24	3.29	3.18	3.38	3.34	2.93	2.73	2.78	2.66	2.88	2.76
Phenol-OMe	3.44	3.28	3.35	3.25	3.38	3.38	2.96	2.77	2.83	2.75	2.82	2.76
Phenolate-enol	2.55	2.57	2.63	2.80	2.92	3.05	2.30	2.39	2.38	2.49	2.31	2.21
Phenolate-OMe	2.55	2.58	2.64	2.82	2.94	3.05	2.31	2.40	2.39	2.50	2.24	2.21
Phenol-enolate	2.09	2.40	2.40	2.77	2.99	2.99	1.76	2.09	1.98	2.21	2.24	2.23
OMe-enolate	2.08	2.39	2.39	2.76	2.95	2.99	1.75	2.08	1.98	2.20	2.25	2.23
Phenolate-enolate	2.42	2.45	2.50	2.58	2.92	2.82	2.01	2.10	2.11	2.11	2.30	2.29

^a Ref 25

be noted that for phenol-keto and its analogue in gas phase, the electronic nature of S₁, after optimization in this state, is not the expected π,π* state but a n,π* dark state with the n orbital centered on the oxygen atom of the keto moiety (Table S6). In fact, the n,π* state is over stabilized in gas phase. For this reason, we do not give the emission energy in gas phase for these derivatives. However, the right ordering of the excited states is recovered when considering the solvent effect, both implicitly or explicitly.

In the following, we will discuss the main differences found between the different formalisms used within the implicit solvation model. Starting with the absorption, we observe that LR, cLR and SS formalisms mostly all underestimate the absorption energies compared to experiment; only for the phenolate-keto form and its analogue the computed values are above the experimental ones, being the energy difference within the method error (≤ 0.06 eV). In Table 1, we observe that the energy differences between E_{LR}^{abs} and E_{cLR}^{abs} are quite small (≤ 0.1 eV). Whereas, the E_{SS}^{abs} are significantly different from the E_{LR}^{abs} and the E_{cLR}^{abs} values, except for phenolate-keto, phenol-enol and their analogues.

It is known that the LR formalism is usually suitable for transitions with low charge transfer (CT) character whereas the SS one gives better results for transitions with large charge rearrangement. For this reason and in order to rationalize the differences found between E_{LR}^{abs} and E_{SS}^{abs} , we have computed the CT character of the absorption transition, that is in the ground state minimum geometry, for all the derivatives (Table 2). In particular, we have calculated the charge of the thiazole group for the ground state equilibrium geometry both, in the ground (S₀) and in the first excited state (S₁). Then, the charge difference (as S₁-S₀) of this group has been calculated, giving an idea of the through-space CT character of the transition (between the thiazole and the benzothiazole moieties).

To support this results, we have made use of a methodology developed to qualitatively investigate the CT from a donor (D) to an acceptor (A) group through a π bridge in push-pulled molecules.^{30,31} The CT distance, d_{CT} , (defined as the distance between the barycenters of the positive and negative regions leading to the CT and the H index (defined as half of the sum of the centroids axis along the π conjugation axis) have been computed (Table 2). By analyzing the calculated CT indexes for the absorption transition (thiazole charge difference, d_{CT} and H index in Table 2 and S4), we can classify the derivatives in three groups: *i*) derivatives with almost negligible CT ($\leq 0.1e$), small d_{CT} and H index close to d_{CT} (indicating a quite small special extent of the CT as shown in Figure S1 by the EDD plots); *ii*) derivatives with CT equal or larger than $0.25e$ with a concomitant large d_{CT} value and *iii*) derivatives with intermediate CT character. It should be noted that for phenolate-enolate, the methodology followed to compute d_{CT} and the H index could not be suitable as this derivative is not a push-pull molecule, as two deprotonated moieties are in each side of the molecule.

Table 2. $S_0 \rightarrow S_1$ and $S_1 \rightarrow S_0$ charge transfer character calculated as the difference of the thiazole ring charges between S_1 and S_0 for the equilibrium geometries in S_0 and S_1 , respectively, using the LR-PCM formalism. The CT distance, d_{CT} , and H index are also given.^{30,31}

		$S_0 \rightarrow S_1$			$S_1 \rightarrow S_0$
		Thiazole Δ charge	d_{CT} (Å)	H (Å)	Thiazole Δ charge
Group 1	Phenol-enol	0.05	1.247	1.086	0.03
	Phenol-OMe	0.03	0.982	0.844	0.01
	OMe-enol	0.07	1.823	1.090	0.05
Group 2	Phenol-keto	0.32	3.732	2.117	0.26
	Phenol-cycle	0.29	3.502	2.269	0.22
	Phenol-enolate	-0.27	3.085	2.514	-0.25
	OMe-enolate	-0.27	3.136	2.612	-0.22
Group 3	Phenolate-enol	0.2	3.253	2.302	0.18
	Phenolate-OMe	0.21	3.276	1.872	0.19
	Phenolate-keto	0.15	2.403	2.123	0.16
	Phenolate-cycle	0.15	2.475	2.289	0.16
	Phenolate-enolate	-0.11	0.995	2.175	-0.11

Following the previous indications, phenol-enol and its analogue belong to the first group as the CT character of the transition is quite small and so d_{CT} . Phenol-keto and phenol-enolate derivatives and their analogues, showing the largest CT character and large d_{CT} values go to the second group. Although these two derivatives are characterized by a large CT character, the nature of the transition however differs: in phenol-keto the charge is transferred from the benzothiazole to the thiazolone ring (Figure 2A), whereas for the phenol-enolate derivatives it is in the opposite direction (Figure 2B). In the third group we

placed the rest of the derivatives that is, the phenolate-keto, phenolate-enol, phenolate-enolate and their analogues, with intermediate CT character.

Figure 2. Natural transition orbitals and electronic density difference (EDD) plots of A) phenol-keto and B) phenol-enolate computed with LR-PCM for the absorption transition. In EDD plots, turquoise and blue colors indicate charge accumulation and depletion, respectively.

Regarding the first group, that is the phenol-enol derivative and its analogue, we observe that the absorption energies computed with the three formalisms (LR, cLR and SS) are quite similar, with energy differences ≤ 0.1 eV. This could be explained by the almost negligible CT character of the transition. If we continue with this reasoning, then for the second group, that is phenol-keto and phenol-enolate, we should find the largest energy differences between E_{LR}^{abs} and E_{SS}^{abs} due to their large CT character. That is, the absorption energy of these derivatives should be the most sensitive to the solvent model chosen. By analyzing the data of Table 1, we can conclude that in fact, the energy differences between E_{LR}^{abs} and E_{SS}^{abs} found for the derivatives of group two are the largest ones ranging, in absolute value, between 0.27-0.37 eV. For the third group, for which the CT character is intermediate, we still observe a clear and halfway effect of the formalism used, finding out that the E_{SS}^{abs} is always larger than E_{LR}^{abs} between 0.13 and 0.24 eV.

Moreover, we can compare the values computed with these three different formalisms to the experimental data (Table 1). As previously argued, for group one the absorption energies computed with the three formalisms are quite similar but, we could say that E_{cLR}^{abs} is the closest to the experiment (energy difference of ≤ 0.05 eV). Then, for groups two and three, as their CT character is quite large, we can guess that the E_{SS}^{abs} will be the closest to the experiment. By analyzing Table 1 we can conclude that this assumption is true for phenolate-enol, phenol-enolate and phenolate-enolate derivatives and their

analogues. Whereas, for the phenolate-keto derivative both the E_{cLR}^{abs} and E_{SS}^{abs} are similar and close to the experimental value (energy difference ≤ 0.1 eV). The exception is phenol-keto and its analogue for which E_{LR}^{abs} is the closest value to the experiment, with an energy difference of ≤ 0.08 eV, being E_{SS}^{abs} red-shifted ~ 0.36 eV. This finding can be explained by the fact that the absorption spectra of phenol-keto is quite different from the one computed for the other derivatives. For phenol-keto and its analogue the absorption spectral band is wide and structured as S_1 and S_2 are quite close in energy, as we have discussed in a recent publication.³⁴ Whereas, for the rest of derivatives the absorption band mainly corresponds to the quite intense S_1 transition (described by a HOMO to LUMO monoexcitation), being in all cases S_2 farther in energy and much lower in intensity. Moreover, for phenol-keto and its analogue the electronic nature of S_1 and S_2 results in a mixture of HOMO to LUMO and HOMO-1 to LUMO monoexcitations. So, the mixed electronic nature of the excited states S_1 and S_2 could be the reason why the SS formalism (considering only S_1) fails on simulating the absorption energies of phenol-keto and its analogue (even though it presents a large CT character), compared to LR or cLR formalisms.

In the following, we perform a similar reasoning for the emission energies. If we compare the emission energies computed with the LR, cLR and SS formalisms (Table 1), we observe that the E_{LR}^{emi} and E_{cLR}^{emi} are quite similar, as observed for the absorption, with energy differences ≤ 0.1 eV except for phenol-keto and its analogue. In order to argue the energy differences found between the three different implicit formalisms, we are going to follow the same reasoning, the CT character, as we did for the absorption energy. By comparing the charge difference of the thiazole moiety for the absorption and emission transitions (Table 2), we observe that their character is quite similar. Hence, we can keep the same groups of molecules regarding their CT character as defined above for the absorption.

In general, we observe trends for E_{LR}^{emi} and E_{SS}^{emi} similar to the ones found for the absorption: for phenol-enol (group one) the energies are similar (≤ 0.07 eV) due to the negligible CT character of this transition (Table 2). For the derivatives of group two (phenol-keto and phenol-enolate), for which there is a large CT in the emission, we found the largest energy differences. Whereas, for the third group that is, derivatives with intermediate CT character, we do not observe a significant energy change (≤ 0.1 eV), contrary to the trend observed for the absorption energy for which a significant energy difference was found for all the compounds included in this group. It should be noted that for the derivatives of the second group the E_{SS}^{emi} is always the closest one to the experiment, being the energy difference ≤ 0.1 eV.

It is known that the computed absolute energy values of the vertical transitions are usually shifted compared to the

experimental values. Therefore, the stokes shift (difference between emission and absorption energies) is usually compared to the experiment. In Table 3 are given the stokes shifts obtained for the different solvation models. All implicit solvation formalisms (LR, cLR and SS) underestimate the experimental stokes shifts. This finding results from the general underestimation of the absorption energy and an overestimation of the emission energy, as already discussed (Table 1). It should be pointed out that in this case, if we consider the zero-point vibrational energy (ZPVE) for computing the absorption and emission energies (ZPEV contribution *ca.* 0.06 eV), the values would be even farther from the experimental results.

Table 3. Stokes shifts in eV for oxyluciferin forms (black) and their analogues (blues) computed in gas phase and with different solvation models. Experimental values are also given.

	$E_{abs}^{theor.} - E_{emi}^{theor.}$ (eV)					Exp ^a
	GP	LR	cLR	SS	QM/MM	
Phenol-keto	1.36	0.32	0.46	0.57	0.91	0.83
Phenol-cycle	1.33	0.32	0.41	0.52	0.81	0.83
Phenolate-keto	0.33	0.18	0.27	0.33	0.51	0.61
Phenolate-cycle	0.31	0.16	0.26	0.31	0.55	0.62
Phenol-enol	0.47	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.65	0.59
OMe-enol	0.48	0.51	0.52	0.50	0.50	0.58
Phenol-OMe	0.46	0.51	0.51	0.52	0.56	0.62
Phenolate-enol	0.25	0.18	0.25	0.31	0.61	0.84
Phenolate-OMe	0.24	0.18	0.25	0.32	0.70	0.84
Phenol-enolate	0.33	0.31	0.42	0.56	0.76	0.76
OMe-enolate	0.33	0.31	0.41	0.56	0.70	0.76
Phenolate-enolate	0.41	0.35	0.39	0.47	0.62	0.53

If we analyze more in detail the values, we observe similar trends for the stokes shifts as the ones found for the absorption and emission energies: *i)* the values computed with the three formalisms for phenol-enol and its analogue are similar and close to the experiment (due to the almost negligible CT character), *ii)* the stokes shifts computed with the SS formalism for the derivatives characterized by a large transfer character (phenol-keto, phenol-enolate and their analogues) are the closest to the experiment and *iii)* for the derivatives with intermediate CT character (group three), the stokes shift computed with the SS formalism is the closest to the experiment but, the differences found with the other formalisms is smaller than the ones found for the derivatives with larger CT character (group two).

Although different implicit formalisms have been tested, still the absorption and emission energies as well as the stokes shifts of some of the derivatives are far from the experimental values (*e.g.* phenolate-enol or phenol-enolate). What we

propose is that, it could be necessary to consider the interaction between the chromophore and the explicit water molecules. For this reason, we have also considered explicitly the solvent to analyze its effect on the absorption and emission energies. The maximum absorption and emission wavelengths obtained from the QM/MM simulated spectra (see Supporting Information and method section) for each derivative are given in Table 1 and the corresponding Stokes shifts in Table 3. The $E_{QM/MM}^{abs}$ and $E_{QM/MM}^{emi}$ are quite close to the experimental values, being the energy difference ≤ 0.13 eV. Also, the Stokes shift values are closer to the experiment when considering explicitly the solvent. So, in general we can conclude that the consideration of explicit water molecules and hence, their interaction with the chromophore, is crucial to reproduce the experimental transition energies.

ii) Absorption and emission spectral shape.

Apart from the calculation of the vertical transition energies (*i.e.* maximum absorption and emission wavelengths), it is also important to analyze the general shape of the spectra. In this section we study the effect of considering: *i)* a statistical number of conformations to simulate the spectra and *ii)* the vibrational normal modes.

In order to compare the effect of considering a statistical number of conformations, the QM/MM simulated spectra have been compared with the ones simulated in gas phase and with the LR-PCM formalism using only one conformation, the minima in the ground or excited state for absorption and emission, respectively.

We have observed three main differences between them. The first one is that structured spectra, such as the absorption spectra of phenol-keto and its analogue, is only well reproduced when considering a statistical number of conformations (Figure 3A and S2A). Moreover, we observe that the absorption bands computed with a statistical number of conformations are wider. A consequence of this finding is that when the first optically bright excited state is relatively close in energy to an upper in energy bright excited state (*e.g.* phenol-enol), the band corresponding to the upper in energy state is hidden in the tail of the most intense band (Figure 3B and S2C). This wide shape of the absorption spectra is in agreement with the experimental ones.²⁵ In addition, for some derivatives there is a clear change of the relative intensities of the different absorption bands when considering a statistical number of conformations. For instance, for phenol-enolate the absorption spectra simulated in gas phase and with the PCM model do not show a higher in energy band corresponding to the excitation to an upper excited state, as its intensity is quite low (Figure 2C and S2D). However, when simulating these spectra with more conformations, a higher in energy band rises, in agreement with the experimental spectra for which it is evident a second absorption band.²⁵

Figure 3. Absorption spectra simulated, in the gas phase (grey) and with the LR-PCM formalism (red) for the ground state minima and with QM/MM methods considering a statistical number of MD snapshots (blue) for A) Phenol-keto, B) Phenol-enol and C) Phenol-enolate derivatives.

Regarding the emission spectra, the main difference observed when considering a statistical number of conformations is that the emission band is wider and not symmetric, showing in some cases the low in energy tail typical of the emission spectra (Figure S3).

In addition, we have studied the effect of the solvent model chosen when including the vibrational information in the spectra simulation. For this aim, we have selected the phenolate-keto form of oxyluciferin due to two reasons. First, it has been pointed out as the most probable chemical form responsible of the emission in bioluminescence.^{39,40} Second, a previous work on the simulation of the vibrational resolved spectra of oxyluciferin⁴¹ states that the phenolate-keto form shows the sharpest peak widths due to the quite intense 0-0' and 0'-0 bands. However, the experimental absorption spectrum is wider, in contrast to this simulated spectrum.

Figure 4. Vibrationally resolved absorption spectra of phenolate-keto in gas phase (black line), in PCM (red line) and for one representative microsolvated snapshot both in gas phase (dash dot blue line) and in PCM (dash blue line). The vibronic transitions of the most intense band (grey shadow) and the following in intensity band (orange shadow) are given as sticks. The vibrational modes, overtones and combination tones of the most intense transitions are depicted (see Supporting Information for the displacement vectors).

The reasoning given in this previous work⁴¹ is that the strong hydrogen-bond interactions between the phenolate-keto and the water molecules around, missing when using the PCM model, could be crucial to reproduce the experimental spectral width.

Aimed by these findings, we have simulated the vibrationally resolved absorption and emission spectra of phenolate-keto in gas phase and with different solvent models: *i*) implicit water with the LR-PCM model and *ii*) using a microsolvation model (considering a small sphere of explicit water molecules around the chromophore) to include the hydrogen-bond interactions. Regarding the microsolvation model, five microsolvated structures (see methods) have been considered for statistical purposes, finding similar results (Figure S5-S12). For this reason, only the spectra simulated for one snapshot (snapshot 4 in Supplementary Information) are shown in the maintext. Both, gas phase and LR-PCM calculations have been performed for these five microsolvated systems.

By analyzing the spectra in Figures 4 and 5, we observe similar trends for the vibrationally resolved absorption and emission spectra. First, the spectra recorded in gas phase (solid black lines) and considering a microsolvation model in gas phase (dash dot blue lines) are wider than the ones computed for the microsolvated or not microsolvated systems with the PCM model (dashed blue line and red line in Figures 4 and 5). In addition, we note that the band following the most intense one (orange shadow in Figures 4 and 5) is significantly more intense for the spectra computed in gas phase.

However, not only the overall shape and width of the spectra have to be analyzed, but also the vibronic transitions responsible of this shape. We can discuss two different effects: *i*) the inclusion of implicit solvation compared to the gas phase and *ii*) the effect of the microsolvation model both in gas phase and in PCM. Starting with the most intense band (grey shadow in Figures 4 and 5), we observe that the 0-0' and 0'-0 transitions are the most intense ones in all cases except for the not microsolvated phenolate-keto in gas phase (black lines).

Moreover, we can analyze the effect of considering an implicit solvent on this band, that is comparing the not microsolvated systems in gas phase and with the PCM model (black and red lines in Figures 4 and 5). We observe that in general all the most intense transitions correspond to the same vibrational modes 3 and 9, their overtones and combination tones (see Figure S13). However, the spectra recorded in PCM is sharper due to the lower intensity of these transitions compared to the 0-0' and 0'-0 ones. Then, if we analyze the effect of the microsolvation model, both in gas phase and with PCM, we observe that the 0-0' and 0'-0 transitions are by far the most intense ones, being the rest of the vibronic transitions quite low in intensity, especially when using the PCM model. So, we can state that including the strong hydrogen-bond interactions does not change the sharper shape of phenolate-keto spectra, contrary to the idea postulated by Hiyama *et al.*⁴¹ However, by comparing the spectra of the microsolvated systems in gas phase and with the PCM model it is clear that a larger number of medium-intense vibronic transitions appear in gas phase, widening the spectra.

Figure 5. Vibrationally resolved emission spectra of phenolate keto in gas phase (black line), in PCM (red line) and for one representative microsolvated snapshot both in gas phase (dash dot blue line) and in PCM (dash blue line). The vibronic transitions of the most intense band (grey shadow) and the following in intensity band (orange shadow) are given as sticks. The vibrational modes, overtones and combination tones of the most intense transitions are depicted (see Figure S13 for the displacement vectors).

A similar analysis can be done for the following in energy band (orange shadow in Figures 4 and 5). Regarding the effect of considering an implicit solvent, we observe that this band is more intense in gas phase. At first, we could think that this finding could be due to a larger and more intense amount of vibronic transitions in this spectral region. However, if we compare the vibronic transitions of the not microsolvated system in gas phase and PCM (black and red sticks in Figures 4 and 5), we observe a similar amount of transitions. However, what makes the difference is that the intensity of these transitions in the PCM spectra is quite low compared to the 0-0' or 0'-0 ones, leading to a less intense band. In addition, we can analyze the effect of considering the microsolvation model. In general, the number of vibronic transitions is reduced when including the microsolvation water but, their intensity is larger thus keeping the overall intensity of this band similar to the corresponding spectra of the not microsolvated systems.

So, we can conclude that including a microsolvation of water molecules, and so the hydrogen-bond interactions between the chromophore and the water molecules, does not change the overall shape of the vibrational resolved absorption and emission spectra of the phenolate-keto derivative. However, a large difference on the relative intensities of the different bands is observed when computing the spectra in gas phase or with the PCM model.

Conclusion

The effect of the solvation model selected for computing the transition vertical energies (both absorption and emission)

could be decisive to get values in agreement with the experimental data. A direct comparison between the simulated and experimental spectra is desired as it allows for obtaining information (electronic nature of the vertical transitions, chemical nature of the chromophore), unaffordable from an experimental point of view. In this work we have demonstrated the key solvent effect on the absorption and emission energies of the different chemical forms of oxyluciferin. In fact, different behaviors have been observed depending on the oxyluciferin derivatives which can be reasoned based on their different CT character. For instance, the SS-PCM formalism is the most suitable to simulate the transition energies of the chemical forms characterized with a significant CT character. On the other hand, the LR-PCM approach is appropriate for computing the transition energies of derivatives with almost negligible CT character. However, still the absolute transition energies are in general far from the experimental value. In this regard, it should be remarked that when considering an explicit solvent model, the computed energies agree with the experimental data.

Apart from the absorption and emission maxima, it is interesting to explore the spectral shape. In this regard, we have checked the effect of considering a statistical number of oxyluciferin-water conformations through QM/MM calculations. We have found that the experimental shape is retrieved only when the spectra is a convolution of the transition energies of different conformations.

Finally, the solvation effect on the vibrational resolved spectra of the phenolate-keto derivative has been studied. We

have found different relative intensities of the bands when doing the calculation in gas phase or with the PCM solvent. However, using a microsolvation model to explicitly consider the solvent and so, the hydrogen bond interactions between the water molecules and oxyluciferin, does not play a role on the spectral shape.

Hence, this work provides a general analysis of the effect of the solvent model chosen on the absorption and emission spectra. In particular, for oxyluciferin it is of great interest as the chemical form responsible for the bioluminescence in fireflies is still under debate. Only when knowing the most suitable solvent method to compute the transition energy, we could get insight into this enigma.

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